

Effect of thermal treatment on the oligomeric size and chaperone activity of α -crystallin

Sudipa Saha^{*a} and K. P. Das^b

^aDepartment of Biotechnology, St. Xavier's College, Kolkata-700 016, India

E-mail : sahasudipa74@yahoo.co.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Bose Institute, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : kalipada@jcbosinst.ac.in, daskp25@gmail.com

Manuscript received 17 February 2015, accepted 26 March 2015

Abstract : α -Crystallin is the major structural protein of eye lens of vertebrates. The intricacy of quaternary association of α -crystallin still remains vague because of its high molecular mass and polydispersity. It is generally believed that oligomerization is pre-requisite for chaperone function, although there is no hard data available on this subject. We therefore undertook a study using temperature as a tool for examining the relationship between oligomeric size and chaperone activity of α -crystallin. Gel filtration experiment showed that α -crystallin existed as low and high molecular mass species. Progressive pre-incubation to higher temperatures dissociated the high molecular mass species to the low molecular mass species. Both light scattering and gel filtration experiment revealed the same finding. Our results also indicate that apart from other age related reasons, simple storage of α -crystallin may lead to formation of high molecular weight aggregated α -crystallin which has very low chaperone activity. One way to prevent the loss of chaperone activity of α -crystallin would be to prevent its further association into larger oligomer.

Keywords : α -Crystallin, molecular chaperone, oligomeric size, thermal aggregation, gel filtration, light scattering.

Introduction

The bovine eye lens consists of three types of soluble proteins : α -, β - and γ -crystallin¹. The intricacy of quaternary association of α -crystallin still remains unclear because of its high molecular mass and polydispersity. Numerous models have been proposed for the quaternary structure of α -crystallin on the basis of known physico-chemical properties. These models are mainly of three types – three-layer assemblies, micelle like structures and assemblies of tetrameric building blocks^{1,2}. Models based on rhombododecahedral structures have also been proposed³. There is no general agreement among the various models. X-Ray structure of α -crystallin is not known. Cryo-electron microscopic investigations of bovine α -crystallin and human α B-crystallin led to re-constructed 3D-images that reveal spherical structures with inner cavities^{4,5}. There seems to be a general agreement that under physiological conditions the quaternary assembly is characterized by a relatively fast subunit exchange indicating a certain degree of conformational flexibility of α -crys-

tallin⁶⁻¹⁰.

α -Crystallin is normally isolated from vertebrate eye lens as an 800 kDa complex. However, various other assemblies ranging from 280 kDa to 10 MDa have been reported^{2,11}. Regardless of subunit composition, all the diverse assemblies efficiently protect other proteins from aggregation. Sometimes temperature assisted dissociation leads to efficient chaperone activity¹². It is believed that oligomeric association of α -crystallin occurs through exposed hydrophobic groups. The hydrophobic exposures of α -crystallin is highly temperature dependent¹³⁻¹⁵. The oligomeric size of α -crystallin also varied with thermal treatment¹⁶. In our study, we used tryptic digestion to change oligomeric size of α -crystallin. The protein was cleaved into pieces and the chaperone activity was enhanced than the full length protein¹⁷. Oligomeric size of α -crystallin can also be varied by varying temperature^{18,19}. Chaperone activity was also found to be affected by temperature changes and pre-incubation^{13,15,20-23}. This gives us an opportunity to study the relationship between oligo-

meric size and chaperone activity by using thermal incubation as a tool to vary oligomeric size without changing the subunit size. We have, therefore, undertaken a study of the oligomeric and chaperone properties of pre-incubated α -crystallin.

Experimental

Materials :

All molecular weight markers such as Thyroglobulin (mol. wt. 669,000), Apoferritin (mol. wt. 443,000), β -Amylase (mol. wt. 200,000), Alcohol dehydrogenase (mol. wt. 150,000), Bovine serum albumin (mol. wt. 66,000) and Carbonic anhydrase (mol. wt. 29,000); Insulin were purchased from Sigma. All buffer salts, Dithiothreitol (DTT) were obtained from SRL.

Isolation and purification of α_H - and α_L -crystallin :

Bovine eye lenses were obtained from a local slaughter house and stored at -80 °C until use. The lenses were homogenized in 10 mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 7.5, containing 0.1 M NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 0.02% NaN_3 and 0.5 mM DTT and centrifuged at $5000 \times g$ at 4 °C for 20 min. The supernatant were fractionated by gel filtration on a column of Sephacryl S-300 HR to get the fraction corresponding to α_H -, α_L -, β_H -, β_L - and γ -crystallin. To get purified α_H - and α_L -crystallin, pooled fractions was loaded on a Sephacryl S-400 HR column. Then it was dialyzed against 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 and stored at -20 °C until required.

Gel filtration experiment :

Individual solutions of α_H - and α_L -crystallin (2 mg/ml) in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2, were incubated at different temperatures between 25 – 70 °C for 1 h and was cooled to room temperature for 1 h. Each sample was loaded on to a superose 6 column (1×45 cm) equilibrated with 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. After loading, the column was eluted with the loading buffer at 0.24 ml/min. The outlet from the column was fed to an on-line UV detector and recorder, which automatically determined the chromatogram by measuring absorbance at 280 nm. Standard molecular weight markers (Thyroglobulin : 669,000; Apoferritin : 443,000; β -Amylase : 200,000; Alcohol dehydrogenase : 150,000; Bovine serum albumin : 66,000 and Carbonic anhydrase : 29,000) were separately run through the column using same conditions. From the elution volume (V_e) of the

individual peaks of the marker proteins, a calibration graph of log MW against V_e/V_0 , where V_0 is the void volume, was generated. Molecular mass of pre-incubated α -crystallin was obtained from this calibration plot using the elution volume.

Light scattering measurements :

Light scattering of α -crystallin solutions were measured using a Hitachi F4500 spectrofluorimeter. For measuring 90° light scattering at respective temperature, 0.2 mg/ml α_L -crystallin (600 μL) in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2, was taken in a fluorescence cuvette placed at a thermostatic cell holder. The solution was heated at respective temperature for 5 min. The 90° scattering of the solution at each temperature was measured using 360 nm as both excitation and emission wavelengths.

For samples of pre-incubated α_L -crystallin of 0.2 mg/ml in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2, the solution was incubated at different temperatures for 1 h and cooled to room temperature for 1 h. Scattering of these solutions was measured as stated above.

Assay of chaperone activity :

Chaperone activity of α_L - and α_H -crystallin, pre-incubated at different temperatures was measured at 25 °C using insulin B-chain aggregation assay. Insulin solution (0.35 mg/ml) in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 was reduced by freshly prepared DTT (final concentration 20 mM) to break the interchain S-S bond leading to the aggregation of the B-chain. Aggregation was monitored in a Shimadzu UV-2401PC spectrophotometer by measuring the apparent absorbance at 400 nm as a function of time. The assay was also performed in presence of 0.175 mg/ml α_H - and α_L -crystallin, pre-incubated at different temperatures.

Results and discussion

Bovine lens on homogenization and gel filtration through Sephacryl S-300 resolved into α_H - and α_L -crystallin along with peaks for β_H -, β_L - and γ -crystallin (Fig. 1). α_H -Crystallin contains high molecular weight (HMW) aggregate of α -crystallin having molecular mass of several million dalton. Change of oligomeric size due to pre-incubation of α -crystallin at various temperatures was monitored by gel filtration experiment. Freshly prepared α_L -crystallin roughly correspond to 800 kDa average molecular mass. However, upon storage at -20 °C for some-

Fig. 1. Sephacryl S-300 HR chromatogram of crystallin proteins of bovine eye lens. Bovine lens was homogenized in 10 mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 7.5, containing 0.1 M NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 0.02% NaN₃ and 0.5 mM DTT, centrifuged at 5000 × g at 4 °C for 20 min; then loaded to the column (1.5 × 95 cm) and eluted in the same buffer at 0.15 ml/min. The fractions were collected from the column and each fraction was 1.0 ml. The fraction α_H represents high molecular weight α -crystallin, α_L represents low molecular weight α -crystallin, β_H represents high molecular weight β -crystallin, β_L represents low molecular weight β -crystallin, γ represents γ -crystallin. β^* is low molecular weight complex of β_L - and γ -crystallin.

time it starts to form HMW. Consequently stored α_L -crystallin showed two peaks, one corresponding to HMW species and the other corresponding to α_L -crystallin (Fig. 2). The molecular mass corresponding to these two peaks was calculated to be approximately 14,000 kDa and 801 kDa. The first peak (14,000 kDa) was due to α_H -crystallin and the second peak (801 kDa) was due to α_L -crystallin. With increase in pre-incubation temperature the area of the first peak decreased while that of the second peak increased. This trend continued up to 57 °C after which the first peak completely disappeared. Only the second peak was observed, but its position slightly shifted towards the right. With further increase in temperature to 70 °C, the peak broadened and the position further shifted to somewhat lower molecular mass range. Thus, the results indicated that with increase in temperature α_H -crystallin was gradually converted to α_L -crystallin.

Another set of gel filtration experiments were carried

Fig. 2. Individual solutions of α_L -crystallin (2 mg/ml) in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2, were incubated at different temperatures between 25–70 °C for 1 h and were cooled to room temperature for 1 h. Each sample was loaded on to a superose 6 column (1 × 45 cm) equilibrated with 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2.

out starting with α_H -crystallin at 25 °C, and pre-incubating it at various temperatures as before. These results were shown in Fig. 3. Here at 25 °C, only a single peak corresponding to 14,000 kDa indicated the presence of HMW α_H -crystallin. Pre-incubation at 50 °C, led an additional broad peak of lower molecular mass. Average mass of α -crystallin aggregates corresponding to this peak was estimated to be 1,000 kDa. Pre-incubation at 57 °C, led to significant reduction in the α_H -crystallin peak. The other peak shifted further right corresponding to average mass of 750 kDa. The increase of pre-incubation temperature to 70 °C completely abolished the α_H -crystallin peak and the single peak of α_L -crystallin corresponded to 600 kDa.

These gel filtration experiments carried out with pre-incubated α_H - and α_L -crystallin revealed two important points. Firstly, storage of α_L -crystallin leads to gradual formation of high molecular weight aggregates. Secondly, on heat treatment, the HMW aggregates dissociate into lower oligomer facilitating conversion of α_H -crystallin to

Fig. 3. Individual solutions of α_{H} -crystallin (2 mg/ml) in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2, were incubated at different temperatures between 25–70 °C for 1 h and were cooled to room temperature for 1 h. Each sample was loaded on to a superose 6 column (1 × 45 cm) equilibrated with 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2.

α_{L} -crystallin.

All of the above measurements were done at room temperature, after cooling the samples pre-heated at various temperatures. The results, therefore, did not reflect upon the oligomeric size of α -crystallin at the respective temperatures. In order to gain information about their relative oligomeric size at various temperatures, we performed light scattering measurement as a function of temperature. Light scattering by macromolecules reflects upon the size of a macromolecular species in solution²⁴ and qualitatively, smaller macromolecules scatter less light than the larger molecules. Fig. 4 showed the 90° light scattering readings of α_{L} -crystallin solution as a function of temperature. It was seen that with increase in temperature, scattering value decreased meaning that oligomeric size of α_{L} -crystallin decreased. For the purpose of comparison, we have done the similar experiment with α_{L} -crystallin pre-incubated at various temperatures (Fig. 5). The trend shown by both sets of data were similar. However, from the quantitative point of view, the slope of the region of sharp fall in scattering in case of pre-incubated samples (Slope ~ 44) was significantly lower than that in case of samples at respective temperatures (Slope ~ 63).

Fig. 4. 90° Light scattering of α_{L} -crystallin as a function of temperature. Scattering was measured in a fluorimeter using 360 nm as both excitation and emission wavelength, taking 0.2 mg/ml protein solution in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2.

Fig. 5. 90° Light scattering of α_{L} -crystallin as a function of pre-incubation temperature. After incubating each solution at the respective temperature for 1 h, the solutions were cooled to 25 °C for 1 h before reading the scattering intensity. Scattering was measured using 360 nm as both excitation and emission wavelength, taking 0.2 mg/ml protein solution in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2.

This revealed that part of the oligomeric structure which was lost during heating was partly regained on cooling. The results clearly demonstrated that oligomeric size decreased upon heat treatment.

The effect of pre-incubation of α -crystallin at various temperatures on its chaperone activity has been studied by utilizing the insulin assay system. We deliberately chose insulin : α -crystallin ratio as 1 : 0.5 (for both α_H - and α_L -crystallin), so that at 25 °C about 25% protection against insulin B-chain aggregation can be achieved in case of α_L -crystallin. When α -crystallin was pre-incubated at 37 °C, the protection increased to 62%. The inset in Fig. 6 showed the percentage protection as a function of temperature. It was seen that at 60 °C nearly full protection could be achieved. Similar experiment has also been done using α_H -crystallin, instead of α_L -crystallin. The results were very similar (Fig. 7). Thus α_H -crystallin whose chaperone activity at 25 °C was low (< 20%), on pre-incubation at 70 °C became fully active.

Our results showed that pre-incubation of α -crystallin reduced its oligomeric size. Both light scattering and gel filtration experiment revealed the same finding. Gel filtration experiment showed that α -crystallin existed as low and high molecular mass species. Progressive pre-

Fig. 6. Chaperone activity of α_L -crystallin at 25 °C by insulin aggregation assay. Assay mixture (600 μ L) contained insulin, 0.35 mg/ml; α_L -crystallin, 0.175 mg/ml and DTT, 20 mM in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. Trace 1, no α_L -crystallin; trace 2, α_L -crystallin pre-incubated at 25 °C; trace 3, α_L -crystallin pre-incubated at 37 °C; trace 4, α_L -crystallin pre-incubated at 45 °C; trace 5, α_L -crystallin pre-incubated at 50 °C; trace 6, α_L -crystallin pre-incubated at 60 °C. Inset shows the percentage of protection as a function of temperature.

Fig. 7. Chaperone activity of α_H -crystallin at 25 °C by insulin aggregation assay. Assay mixture (600 μ L) contained insulin, 0.35 mg/ml; α_H -crystallin, 0.175 mg/ml and DTT, 20 mM in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. Trace 1, no α_H -crystallin; trace 2, α_H -crystallin pre-incubated at 25 °C; trace 3, α_H -crystallin pre-incubated at 37 °C; trace 4, α_H -crystallin pre-incubated at 50 °C; trace 5, α_H -crystallin pre-incubated at 60 °C; trace 6, α_H -crystallin pre-incubated at 70 °C. Inset shows the percentage of protection as a function of temperature.

incubation to higher temperatures dissociated the high molecular mass species to the low molecular mass species. Previous studies on the effect of heating on the oligomeric size reported somewhat different results^{10,16}. Siezen *et al.* (1980) reported that oligomeric size decreased on increasing temperature from 25 °C to 37 °C. Beyond this temperature, they reported an increase in size due to aggregation. Putilina *et al.* (2003) demonstrated from small angle X-ray scattering data an irreversible doubling of molecular weight and a corresponding increase in size of α -crystallin at temperatures above 60 °C. A similar observation has also been reported by Burgio *et al.* (2000). Such a trend was not observed in our study. Our data showed that in terms of heating and cooling on a broad time scale, high and low molecular mass aggregates seem to be interconvertible. However, an increased activity of α -crystallin was reported by Burgio *et al.* (2000) after a cycle of heating and cooling, which was attributed to the conformation and packing parameters of α -crystallin in the oligomeric assembly. The G98R mutation in αA -crystallin produced unstable oligomers and the chaperone ac-

tivity of the dissociated subunits suggested that the α A-crystallin subunits were the minimal units of chaperone activity²⁶. The P39R mutation at the N-terminal domain of α B-crystallin is important for oligomerization and chaperone function²⁷. The absence of residues 54–61 in alphaB-crystallin significantly decreased the oligomeric mass of alphaB-crystallin and showed increased hydrophobicity and enhanced chaperone activity²⁸.

Our main objective of this study was to study the chaperone activity of intact α -crystallin whose oligomeric size was varied by pre-incubation. Both gel filtration as well as light scattering experiments indicated reduction in the size of α _H- or α _L-crystallin oligomer with increase of pre-incubation temperature. Our chaperone assay study indicated increase of chaperone activity with increase of temperature. Thus it turns out that oligomeric size bears an inverse relationship with chaperone activity. As was shown earlier, pre-incubation of α -crystallin enhanced surface hydrophobicity as new pockets were exposed and exposed hydrophobicity correlated well with chaperone activity¹³. Our previous study showed that hydrophobicity is an important parameter and oligomeric size is less important for chaperone activity¹⁷. The observation of higher chaperone activity of lower sized oligomer of α _L-crystallin confirmed that hydrophobicity, and not oligomeric size, is important determinant of chaperone activity of α -crystallin²⁹. Our results also indicate that apart from other age related reasons, simple storage of α -crystallin may lead to formation of high molecular weight aggregated α -crystallin which has very low chaperone activity. One way to prevent the loss of chaperone activity of α -crystallin would be to prevent its further association into larger oligomer.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Mr. Dipak Chandra Konor, Lab. Technician, Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, Kolkata, for help with the experiments.

References

1. R. C. Augusteyn and A. Stevens, *Prog. Polymer Sci.*, 1998, **23**, 375.
2. P. J. T. A. Groenen, K. B. Merck, W. W. de Jong and H. Bloemendal, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1994, **225**, 1.
3. G. Wistow, *Exp. Eye Res.*, 1993, **56**, 729.
4. D. A. Haley, J. Horwitz and P. L. Stewart, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1998, **277**, 27.
5. D. A. Haley, M. P. Bova, Q. L. Huang, H. S. Mchaourab and P. L. Stewart, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 2000, **298**, 261.
6. S. Abgar, N. Yevlampieva, T. Aerts, J. Vanhoudt and J. Clauwaert, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 2000, **276**, 619.
7. M. P. Bova, L. L. Ding, J. Horwitz and B. K. Fung, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1997, **272**, 29511.
8. S. A. Datta and C. M. Rao, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2000, **275**, 41004.
9. M. Ehrnsperger, H. Lilie, M. Gaestel and J. Buchner, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1999, **274**, 14867.
10. T. Putilina, F. Skouri-Panet, K. Prat, N. H. Lubsen and A. Tardieu, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2003, **278**, 13747.
11. T. H. MacRae, *Cell. Mol. Life Sci.*, 2000, **57**, 899.
12. M. Haslbeck, S. Walke, T. Stromer, M. Ehrnsperger, H. E. White, S. X. Chen, H. R. Saibil and J. Buchner, *EMBO J.*, 1999, **18**, 6744.
13. K. P. Das and W. K. Surewicz, *FEBS Lett.*, 1995, **369**, 321.
14. B. Raman, T. Ramakrishna and C. M. Rao, *FEBS Lett.*, 1995, **365**, 133.
15. B. Raman and C. M. Rao, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1994, **269**, 27264.
16. R. J. Siezen, J. G. Bindels and H. J. Hoenders, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1980, **111**, 435.
17. S. Saha and K. P. Das, *Proteins*, 2004, **57**, 610.
18. M. R. Burgio, P. M. Bennett and J. F. Koretz, *Mol. Vision*, 2001, **7**, 228.
19. J. Vanhoudt, S. Abgar, T. Aerts and J. Clauwaert, *Biochemistry*, 2000, **39**, 4483.
20. J. Bhattacharyya and K. P. Das, *Biochem. Mol. Biol. Int.*, 1998, **46**, 249.
21. B. K. Das J. J. N. Liang and B. Chakraborti, *Curr. Eye Res.*, 1997, **16**, 303.
22. G. B. Reddy, K. P. Das, J. M. Petrash and W. K. Surewicz, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2000, **275**, 4565.
23. S. A. Datta and C. M. Rao, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1999, **274**, 34773.
24. C. Tanford, "Physical Chemistry of Macromolecules", John Wiley & Sons, 1961.
25. M. R. Burgio, C. J. Kim, C. C. Dow and J. F. Koretz, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 2000, **268**, 426.
26. M. Raju, P. Santhoshkumar and K. K. Sharma, *Mol. Vis.*, 2011, **17**, 7.
27. N. Numoto, A. Kita, N. Fujii and K. Miki, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 2012, **425**, 601.
28. P. Santhoshkumar, R. Murugesan and K. K. Sharma, *Biochemistry*, 2009, **48**, 5066.
29. S. Saha and K. P. Das, *Protein J.*, 2007, **26**, 315.